

HIGH POWER DENSITY AXIAL FLUX ON-BOARD MOTOR AND DRIVE SERIES

EM-TECH

Politecnico di Torino

The developed solution guarantees thermal integrity, while reducing friction losses.

Power density increase of proposed solution, while preventing irreversible demagnetization

CHALLENGES & SOLUTION:

Indirect cooling concept: The challenge was to design and optimize a novel indirect cooling strategy based on a cold plate for the rotor of the yokeless axial in-wheel motor. The motivation for choosing this solution is the reduction of the large friction losses at high speeds present in the current direct cooling strategy. The objectives were minimizing the pressure drops, while maximizing the heat extraction in the system to boost the performance of the machine. Beginning from a computational fluid dynamics model of diverse potential solutions, the design was iteratively refined in collaboration with our project partner, TRAXIAL, who is building the prototype. The solution includes a hollow cooling shaft that conducts the coolant in the cold plates, which also was refined to reduce pressure drops.

Results show a large reduction in the magnet hotspot temperature compared with an air forced convection cooling strategy without the significant friction losses present in the baseline direct cooling strategy. Thus, reducing the risk of irreversible demagnetization while pushing the power density of the EM-TECH axial in-wheel motor.

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

The developed cooling system allows the EM-TECH axial flux motor to reach high-power density levels, while preserving the thermal integrity of the machine and mitigating the hydraulic losses of the baseline cooling strategy. Future work is towards the optimization of the structure to increase the maximum speed to achieve higher power density levels.

Figure 1: Temperature contour of the EM-TECH axial flux motor with cold plate rotor cooling at steady-state: 12 krpm and 200 Nm.

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